

Information Sheet and Consent form for “Perspectives, Needs and Challenges for Sustainable Software Engineering Teams: A FinServ Case Study.”

About the study:

This is a pilot exploratory study funded by COMPANY to understand what does sustainability in general and sustainability for software engineering mean for a Large-Scale Financial Organization and to the software engineering practitioners within this organization. This will help us understand what the needs, opportunities, challenges and threats are to achieve sustainability for software engineering teams.

What will your participation involve:

This study will be conducted in the form of interviews, either one-on-one or as a focus group. All the participants are divided into two groups, where one-on-one interviews are conducted for group 1, while group 2 will be interviewed in a focus group. Please note that the entire interview might be voice and/or video recorded and with some notes taken by investigators during the interview.

As a participant in this study, you will be automatically assigned to either of or both the groups depending upon your job role. This is done to ensure there are diverse sets of participants in both the groups. You can at any time ask to be placed in any of the groups, and it shall be accommodated accordingly if places exist. By the end of the study, your participation will be taken in the form of either one interview, or one focus group, or one interview and one focus group.

As a participant in this study, you have the right to withdraw and request all your responses to be removed at any time during the participation period.

One-on-one interviews will be held for 30 minutes maximum, where a set of questionnaires will be asked. Please note that there are no right or wrong answers to these questions. We ask these questions to understand your perspective. You may wish not to answer any/all these questions if you wish to.

Each focus group contains 5 participants and will be held for 1 hour maximum. There will be a set of questionnaires and perspectives of all the participants are taken together. Please note that there are no right or wrong answers to these questions. We ask these questions to understand your perspective. You may wish not to answer any/all these questions if you wish to.

All the responses recorded will be anonymized by removing all the personally identifiable information, held confidentially in a password (online) and lock (offline) protected environment and will only be accessed by investigators of this study. Please note that none of these responses will be shared with the organization. If audio/video recordings are made, after the interview these recordings will be transcribed as soon as possible, and only these text transcriptions are stored while raw recordings are deleted permanently. These text transcriptions may be retained for future use.

Please note that any findings from this study might be published and shared in the proceedings of a conference.

If you have any further questions or concerns, please contact any member of the research team at any stage of the study (contact information below).

Investigator 1: Anonymous,
UNIVERISTY

Investigator 2: Anonymous
UNIVERISTY

Investigator 3: Anonymous
UNIVERISTY

Investigator 4: Anonymous
COMPANY

I have read this information sheet and give my consent to voluntarily take part in this study.

Name: _____

Email: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____